

IMMEDIATE EFFECTS OF PROLONGED KNEEL-SITTING ON STATIC AND DYNAMIC BALANCE IN HEALTHY YOUNG ADULTS

Mazahir Zia^{*1}, Muhammad Asif², Kanwal Lalwani³, Shamsa Abdul Rehman⁴, Manahil Amir⁵,
Sadiah Mazahir⁶

¹Department of Health, Physical Education and Sports Sciences, University of Karachi, Karachi

²Department of Rehabilitation and Health Sciences, Nazeer Hussain University, Karachi

³Isra Institute of Rehabilitation Sciences, Isra University, Hyderabad

⁴South City Institute of Physical Therapy and Rehabilitation

⁵ Helping Hand for Relief and Development, Bahawalpur

⁶ Department of Physical Therapy, Mamji Hospital, Karachi

^{*1}mzia@uok.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Mazahir Zia

Abstract

Background: Kneel-sitting, including the traditional Seiza posture, is very common in many Asian and Middle Eastern domestic, cultural and occupational situations. Although such positions may facilitate floor level activities, sustained knee flexed positions can influence lower limb circulation, trunk muscle behavior, proprioceptive input and postural responses after such positions. However, evidence regarding their immediate effect on balance in healthy young adults remains scarce.

Objective: To assess the immediate effects of prolonged kneel sitting on static and dynamic balance in healthy young adults.

Methods: A repeated measures experimental study was conducted in Karachi, Pakistan; comprising of 30 asymptomatic young adults aged 17-25 years. Participants adopted a kneel sitting posture; similar to traditional Seiza posture; for 30 minutes per day for three consecutive days. Static balance was assessed with the Stork Stand Test (SST) and dynamic balance was assessed with the Star Excursion Balance Test (SEBT) in all eight directions for both limbs. Pre and post exposure values were analyzed in SPSS version 21 using paired samples comparisons. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The mean age of participants was 20.53 ± 1.43 years consisting 56.7% of male participants. Static balance improved after kneel sitting position on both the right leg ($7.67 \pm 4.00s$ to $10.07 \pm 11.00s$; $p < 0.001$) and left leg ($8.10 \pm 7.00s$ to $11.13 \pm 15.00s$; $p < 0.001$). On the other hand, dynamic balance results showed a decline across most SEBT directions. The decrease was more consistent and robust on the right side ($p < 0.001$), whereas the left side also showed significant reductions in multiple directions ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Prolonged kneel sitting appeared to improve static balance modestly while reducing dynamic balance performance significantly.

Introduction

Contemporary work and living patterns usually encounter individuals to prolonged, sustained and mechanically constrained postures/positions. In many occupational environments, kneel sitting remain necessary for task completion and prolonged exposure to such positions has been related to musculoskeletal pain, sickness absence and longer term joint degeneration e.g osteoarthritis [1-4]. In parallel, floor-based positions also remain embedded in domestic, cultural and religious practices in Asia and the Middle East, including Pakistan. Despite their ubiquity, short-term functional consequences of such postures are still underexplored in physical therapy and ergonomics research studies[5-8].

Human posture is an active and complex process that is controlled by neuromuscular coordination, proprioceptive feedback, joint position and balance control. Sustained sitting in one position decreases muscular and joint motion thus decreasing the proprioceptive information to the central nervous system and increasing the susceptibility of muscle fatigue and imbalance. The electro-myographic studies have also shown that the long term postural loading changes muscle activity, recruitment techniques and coordination of muscles. Also, postural deviations were associated with respiratory dysfunction and loss of body control, which demonstrates the overall effect of the system of prolonged immobility [9-11]. For this reason, a posture may appear mechanically stable in static testing while impairing dynamic balance during functional movement transitions at the same time.

Kneel sitting warrants particular attention in this regard because it places the hips, knees, ankles and feet in prolonged maximally/fully flexed positions. Biomechanical researches suggest that kneeling may preserve spinal alignment better than some asymmetrical floor sitting styles [5,6], while physiological studies show that sustained Seiza position can reduce lower limb oxygenation, raise sensory thresholds and increase body sway after standing [7]. More recently, kneel sitting has shown significant calf hypoperfusion in healthy young adults, suggesting

a plausible vascular mechanism for transient postural instability after rising up from this position [8].

The broader literature on prolonged sitting and static posture also supports the relevance of this question. Prolonged sitting behavior has been found associated with poorer general health, higher cardiometabolic risk and musculoskeletal discomfort [12-14]. In task specific settings, floor based sitting postures have been associated with trunk muscle fatigue and discomfort, while occupational kneel sitting, squat sitting and similar knee straining postures have been related to knee osteoarthritis and related disability [2-4,15]. These observations suggest posture not simply a cultural preference but a clinically meaningful exposure with consequences for physical functioning.

A further point of concern is fatigue related impairment in dynamic balance. Reviews and experimental studies depict that physical fatigue can worsen postural sway and dynamic balance performance of activities, particularly when tests demand coordinated multi-joint control [16,17]. If prolonged kneel sitting induces even mild lower limb fatigue, circulatory restriction or sensory-motor compromise, it may preferentially affect dynamic. This study was undertaken to examine the immediate effects of prolonged kneel sitting on static and dynamic balance in healthy young adults. The hypothesis was that kneel sitting would alter postural control after standing, with more pronounced effects on dynamic balance than on static balance.

Methodology

This study used a repeated measures pre-post experimental design. Participants. Thirty asymptomatic young adults aged 17–25 years were recruited from the general population of Karachi, Pakistan through convenience sampling. Written informed consent was obtained before participation. Participants with metabolic, systemic, musculoskeletal or neurological disorders and those unwilling to participate were excluded.

Intervention protocol

Participants were instructed to attain a kneel sitting position for 30 minutes daily over three consecutive days with a 24-hour interval between sessions. Kneel sitting was defined as sitting on the heels with hips and knees flexed and the lower legs positioned beneath the thighs, similar to traditional Seiza posture described in the ergonomics literature [7,18]. Participants were familiarized with all testing procedures before data collection.

Outcome measures

Static balance was assessed using the Stork Stand Test. Participants stood on the dominant limb with hands on the hips while balancing on the ball of the foot, and the best of three trials was recorded in seconds. Dynamic balance was assessed using the Star Excursion Balance Test (SEBT), a widely used functional test of dynamic postural control with good reliability in healthy adults [11,12]. Reach distances were recorded in eight directions; anterior, anteromedial, medial, posteromedial, posterior, posterolateral, lateral, and anterolateral; for both limbs. Limb length was measured from the anterior superior iliac spine to the medial malleolus, and normalized reach distance was calculated as [(excursion distance / limb length) × 100], consistent with accepted SEBT methodology [19,20]. Static balance was evaluated through Stork Stand Test (SST). Participants stood on each leg with their

hands on their hips and maintained balance on the ball of the foot. Three trials were performed and longest duration in seconds was recorded [21,22].

Data analysis

Data were analyzed with SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics summarized participant demographic characteristics. Pre-post comparisons were performed using paired samples analyses. Significance threshold was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Thirty participants completed the study. The mean age of participants was 20.53 ± 1.43 years (range, 17–23 years), and 17 participants (56.7%) were males while 13 (43.3%) were females. Static balance improved after kneel sitting intervention, whereas dynamic balance showed a consistent downward pattern across the majority of SEBT directions.

Mean Stork Stand (Static Balance) time increased from 7.67 ± 4.00 s to 10.07 ± 11.00 s on right leg and from 8.10 ± 7.00 s to 11.13 ± 15.00 s on left leg. These changes correspond to relative increases of approximately 31.3% and 37.4%, respectively. The source analysis showed statistically significant pre-post differences for both sides (Right: $p < 0.001$; Left: $p < 0.001$). (Table-1)

Table-1. Static balance Scores before and after kneel sitting.

Leg	Pre-intervention time (seconds)	Post-intervention time (seconds)	Absolute change (Seconds)	p value
Right	7.67	10.07	+2.40	$p < 0.001$
Left	8.10	11.13	+3.03	$p < 0.001$

Statistical analysis of dynamic balance for the right leg expressed a consistent reduction in reach distance in most directions at post intervention assessment; particularly in the anterior, anteromedial, medial, and posteromedial

directions. The mean reach distance across all eight directions decreased from 90.38cm pre to 89.25cm post exposure. Although absolute changes were modest in some directions, the source analysis reported statistically significant differences for all right leg directions ($p < 0.001$).

Table-2: Right leg SEBT scores pre and post kneel sitting.

SEBT direction (right)	Pre-intervention (cm)	Post-intervention (cm)	p value
Anterior	91	89	p<0.001
Anteromedial	90	88	p<0.001
Medial	83	81	p<0.001
Posteromedial	89	87	p<0.001
Posterior	96	95	p<0.001
Posterolateral	93	92	p<0.001
Lateral	90	91	p<0.001
Anterolateral	91	91	p<0.001

Similarly, analysis of Dynamic balance for the left leg again shown that overall pattern favored decreased post-intervention reach distances. The mean reach distance in all eight directions decreased from 88.88cm pre-intervention to 87.88cm post-intervention. Largest detected

decrements were in the anteromedial and lateral directions. Considering the source analysis, all directions showed statistically significant differences, with p values less than or equal to 0.005. (Table-3; Figure-1)

Table-3: Left-leg SEBT pre and post kneel sitting

SEBT direction (left)	Pre-intervention (cm)	Post-intervention (cm)	p value
Anterior	89	89	p<0.001
Anteromedial	89	87	p=0.005
Medial	84	83	p<0.001
Posteromedial	87	86	p<0.001
Posterior	93	92	p<0.001
Posterolateral	91	90	p<0.001
Lateral	89	87	p<0.001
Anterolateral	89	89	p=0.001

Figure-1: Left-leg SEBT performance pre and post kneel sitting.

Discussion

This study investigated the immediate effects of prolonged kneel sitting on balance in healthy young adults of Karachi. The principal findings were towards a divergent postural response; static single leg balance improved after intervention, whereas dynamic balance shown a significant decline. This pattern is clinically very important expressing that a posture may appear stable during quiet static stance while still reducing dynamic stability during functional tasks that require controlled movement transitions.

The improvement in static balance may reflect mechanical and neuromuscular characteristics of the assumed sitting position. Experimental studies on floor sitting styles indicate that kneel sitting can improve postural and spinal stability than some asymmetrical floor sitting postures, particularly when compared with positions that employ trunk rotation or greater pelvic asymmetry [5]. Radiographic evidence also shows that Japanese style kneel sitting preserves a spinopelvic orientation closer to upright standing than cross legged sitting [6]. These features may augment short-term passive/static stability and explain the longer Stork Stand times observed after the kneel sitting exposure in the present study.

In contrast, dynamic balance demonstrated a consistent downward response. This is a physiologically plausible reaction. Dynamic postural control requires quick sensorimotor integration, adequate perfusion of blood in lower limb, intact joint proprioception and coordinated muscle recruitment. Classic studies on Seiza showed that traditional kneel sitting can reduce lower-limb oxygenation, increase plantar sensory thresholds and increase postural sway after longer duration standing [2]. More recent evidence confirms that kneel sitting can markedly reduce calf muscle perfusion, most likely through vascular kinking and soft tissue compression [8]. Together, these mechanisms may transiently compromise lower limb sensory and motor responses needed for optimal SEBT performance; directly related to functional daily living activities. Fatigue related explanations are also relevant in this regard. Dynamic balance appears more

sensitive than static balance to acute fatigue in many experimental research contexts [16,17]. Reviews on fatigue and SEBT/Y-balance test performance have reported that post-fatigue dynamic balance deficits are more likely in healthy and recreationally active subjects than deficits in simpler static tasks [16]. Similarly, experimental work on physical fatigue in healthy young adults shows increased postural sway and reduced dynamic balance adjustment efficiency after fatiguing tasks [17]. Although the current study did not measure muscle fatigue or local oxygenation, the kneel sitting position may have produced a mild, position induced neuromuscular and vascular state inducing fatigue that selectively affected dynamic control. The present study findings should also be interpreted in context of ergonomics and its relation to long term musculoskeletal exposure. Occupational kneel sitting and squat sitting are recognized risk factors for knee joint symptoms and osteoarthritis [1,4]. Meta-analyses shows that kneeling, squatting, heavy lifting, and other knee-straining activities are consistently associated with knee osteoarthritis [2], while floor based cultural postures, for example squatting and lotus sitting, have been associated with radiographic knee osteoarthritis in habitual users [3]. The current findings do not demonstrate long-term joint damage, but they do add a predictive functional perspective: even short term exposure to a kneelsitting posture may measurably alter balance performance.

The broader sitting behavior evidence further supports concern about prolonged static postures. Prolonged sitting has been associated with poorer general health and adverse outcomes in observational research studies [12-14]. In more task specific ergonomic studies, floor based or constrained sitting postures are found related with trunk discomfort and lower back muscle fatigue and pain [15,23]. For clinicians and other health practitioners, these data reinforce that posture exposure should be considered both from a cumulative musculoskeletal perspective as well as from an immediate functional perspective.

An interesting observation of the current data is apparent separation between static and dynamic

balance. This supports the previous view that static and dynamic balance tests are not interchangeable and should not be interpreted as a single measuring construct [19,20,23]. In practical terms, a worker, student or worshipper who stands up from a prolonged kneel sitting position may not look overtly unstable in static standing yet may still experience a mild transient decline in movement related postural control. Physiotherapists should therefore consider dynamic balance assessment when evaluating individuals exposed to prolonged floor based postures.

Limitations and recommendations

This study has some limitations as well. First, the sample was small and selected by convenience sampling, which limits generalizability. Second, the participants were healthy young adults; the findings may not apply to older adults, symptomatic individuals or workers with long-term occupational exposure. Third, the design did not include a control group, so findings are interpreted as pre-post associations following kneel sitting position rather than definitive causal effects. Fourth, the study assessed immediate changes only and did not examine longer persistence of the balance changes. Finally, the balance measures were practical clinical tests rather than instrumented posture-graphy and source dataset did not include direct measurements of muscle fatigue, circulation or proprioception. Future studies should include larger samples, occupationally exposed populations, instrumented balance assessment and comparison of different floor based postures and exposure durations.

Clinical implications

From a clinical physiotherapy perspective, individuals who frequently adopt kneel sitting postures should be advised to vary their postures, perform intermittent movements and avoid prolonged uninterrupted flexed postures. Where kneel sitting is culturally or occupationally unavoidable, graded lower limb conditioning, ankle foot mobility work and balance oriented exercises may help reduce transient instability

after standing. In occupational settings, ergonomic task redesigning, use of supportive surfaces/equipment, scheduled micro breaks and posture alteration strategies may be particularly useful. Dynamic balance screening testing should also be considered in populations with repeated exposures, especially when the work environment contains slip or rapid transition demands.

Conclusion

Prolonged kneel sitting was associated with a slight improvement in static balance but a significant reduction in dynamic balance in healthy young adults. The findings suggest that kneel sitting may temporarily enhance static single leg stability slightly while simultaneously impairing functional postural control.

These results are clinically relevant for physiotherapists, ergonomists and occupational health practitioners working with people who routinely kneel for cultural, domestic or vocational reasons. Posture alterations, ergonomic modifications and physical conditioning should be considered to minimize transient functional instability and potential injury risk following prolonged kneel sitting exposures.

Ethical considerations

Participants were informed about the purpose and procedures of the study, written consent was signed by each participant and confidentiality of participants' data was maintained for research and publication purposes. Researchers also made it sure to align with the guidelines of Declaration of Helsinki.

Conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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